

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH OF LEXICOGRAPHY ISSUES IN TURKOLOGY AND AZERBAIJANI LINGUISTICS

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Abstract

In the article it has been dealt with the investigation of lexicography issues in Turkology and Azerbaijani linguistics. The specific, clear and correct expression of different linguistic concepts of the terms related to the science of linguistics shows that the science of linguistics is at a high level of development. Scientific development in our modern times is also reflected in the researches in the field of Turkology. In the article information has also been given about well-known scientists, researchers and their works who have conducted serious research in the field of general linguistics in Azerbaijan and have a special place in Azerbaijani linguistics. In-depth research, analysis and scientific summarization of the onomastic lexicon, which has a special place in the vocabulary of the language, helps to solve the complex and necessary issues of our language and history. The information have been given about the works of Turkologists who dealt with the most relevant problems not only with one branch of linguistics, but also with phonetics, orthography, etymology, historical grammar, morphology, syntax, speech culture, etc.

Keywords: turkology, Azerbaijani linguistics, issues of lexicography, general linguistics, onomastic lexicon, linguistic concepts, the vocabulary of the language

Turkology is as a field of humanities studies the history, languages, literature, folklore, ethnology of the Turks in a comparative way. Turkology is a scientific field that gained a system on the basis of oriental studies, which emerged as a result of the West's attempts to study the East. The vast majority of turkological information about the Middle Ages is available to us thanks to the works of Byzantine/Greek scholars, historians, ambassadors, geographers and travelers.

As we know, the lexical layer of the language consists of two parts: general function and special function. Noted these two functional parts complete each other in the formation of the lexical layer of the language. The linguistic units, which are the basis in its creation of the terminological system, performing the special function of the language cause the formation of the system. The terms, which are linguistic elements of the terminological system, differ from other elements in the language system according to their specific characteristics, and the terms play a decisive role in the formation of the scientific style of the language. For this reason, the terms organize a terminological system in the sense of a sign of scientific concepts. A collection of terms belonging to different fields creates a terminological system. The terms belonging to the science of linguistics form an exhausted and full opinion idea about the science to which it belongs. The concrete, clear and correct expression of different linguistic concepts of terms related to the science of linguistics shows that it is at a high level of development. There are two concepts that we often encounter in the scientific literature: "linguistic terms" and the term "linguistic terminology". One of the first works of the world of linguistics is Mahmud Kashghari's "Divanu Lughat-it-Turk", which is considered an encyclopedia of Turkology. Ethnological information about the Turks was systematized for the first time in the 11th century by the Turkish philologist

Mahmud Kashghari in the work "Divanu Lughat-it-Turk". This work was written primarily to fulfill the function of teaching the Arabs this language. Only the features of the Turkish language were not analyzed in the work, at the same time, the philologist, who knows the Arabic language well enough, analyzed the specific characteristics of the Arabic language to the smallest details. In the work of M. Kashghari, a large number of terms related to various fields of science have been used. Among the linguistic terms used in the work, the following terms were used: yazı - "writing", kileçü - "word", kok - "root", "main", "ring", "syllable", etc. [9. p. 235]. Multilingual dictionaries began to appear in the thirteenth century, when trade expanded even more.

"Turk-tatar dilinin grammatikasi", («Турецко-татарского Грамматика») written by Mirze Kazymbey in 1839, as well as "Turk-tatar dilinin umumi grammatikasi" published in 1946 play an important role in Azerbaijani linguistics. The information about the grammatical structure of the Azerbaijani language was given clearly and extensively in these works. The information reflected in this work is one of the excellent sources that maintain the importance of grammar. *The work written by M. Kazym bey was evaluated as a new phenomenon not only in Azerbaijani linguistics, but also in all Turkic languages [1, p.35].* As Y.M. Seyidov mentioned, *Mirza Kazim bey's grammar preceded dozens of works on the grammatical structure of the Turkish language by a century. During the research, it did not escape our notice that M. Kazymbey's («Турецко-татарского Грамматика») "Turk-tatar dilinin grammatikasi" is also called the grammar of the Azerbaijani language [9, p. 265].*

During the period of P.A. Pallas, the investigation of the Turkish language was further developed. In his work "Butun dillərin mugayisəli lugheti" he also gave

characteristics of Mishar, Tatar, Nogai, Bashkir and other Turkic ethnic groups of Turks.

In the 19th century, Mirza Kazim Bey played an important role in the development of Turkology. The above-mentioned work written by him was a fundamental scientific discovery of its time. [10]. By the end of the 19th century, the science of Turkology had already entered the fields of science such as history, philology, folklore studies, archeology, ethnology. And in the 20th century, Turkology entered such fields of science as physical anthropology, numismatics, genetics, ancient Turkish alphabets, typology, genesis, etymology, onomastics and toponomics.

An important feature of enlightenment in Azerbaijan at the end of the 19th century was closely related to natural science. In this regard, the creativity of the outstanding educator, naturalist, cultural figure, pedagogue, talented publicist Hasan Bey Zardabi is typical. He is considered the founder of the democratic press in Azerbaijan, which comes from national self-awareness. The publication of the first "Akinchi" newspaper in the Azerbaijani language on July 22, 1875 is connected with his name, and this newspaper was being published between 1875 and 1877. In his works with philosophical content, his views on enlightenment and natural science have been reflected in the following works: "Torpag, su ve hava", "Barama gurdunun saxlanmasi", "Gigiyena hagginda", "Ayn fazalarimin yerde uzvu hayata tesiri", "Bedeni selamat saxlamaq dusturuemeldir". In addition, his articles that were published in "Akinchi" newspaper are also important in this regard.

H.B. Zardabi paid attention to other means, such as theater, in addition to charitable societies in the field of educated and enlightened the people and the young generation. At the same time, H.B. Zardabi attracts attention with his educational and social philosophical ideas. He saw the progress and happiness of his people in science, enlightenment, and the development of education. Qualities such as humanism, patriotism, and truthfulness took the main place in his educational views.

Modern scientific developments allow us to use calibrating, dendrochronology, metallurgy, chemistry, textiles and other fields for help in research in the field of Turkology. Among the representatives engaged in the scientific research of the Azerbaijani language B. Chobanzade, J. Khandan, M. Jafar, M. Shiraliyev, A. Demirchizade, M. Huseynzade, A. Orujov, S. Jafarov, A. Abdullayev, F. Zeynalov, and in later times A. Akhundov, T. Hajiyev, Y. Seyidov, N. Jafarov and other linguists have been trained, and served the scientific development of the language. Living the values formed by the nation for thousands of years, language is also an important event for the transmission of these values to the younger generations.

Language is an important event for the survival of the values formed by the nation for thousands of years and for the transmission of these values to the younger generations. Therefore, language is not only a means of communication, but also a system of values. It should be emphasized that the existence of the literary language is an important factor in the development of the

state language, and poets and writers have made great contributions in this direction. At the same time, the name of many intellectuals can be mentioned. However, the incomparable services of Mirza Ibrahimov, an outstanding Azerbaijani intellectual, a fighter for the national language, and the late academician, should be remembered with special respect.

After the restoration of state independence in 1991, he had an exceptional role in establishing the Azerbaijani language as the state language in the Constitution adopted by referendum on November 12, 1995.

Compared to the traditional fields of language science (language-production or linguistics) in Azerbaijan, the study of general or theoretical linguistics on a scientific basis started relatively late – in 1919, with the establishment of the Department of General Linguistics of Baku State University. The most important reason for this that Azerbaijani linguistics has been under the influence of the Arabic school of linguistics since the Middle Ages. The main priority direction in the study of language in Eastern countries was lexicography – vocabulary. Prominent Turkologist Professor Bekir Chobanzadeh conducting research in the aspects of general linguistics and Turkology laid the foundation for a new stage of linguistic development in Azerbaijan in the 1920s. B. Chobanzade, who has a rich and multifaceted theoretical and philological heritage, perfectly knows Arabic, Persian, Russian, English, German, French, Hungarian, Czech, Polish, Georgian and Slavic languages, including all dialects and local languages of the Turkish languages served unparalleled services in the research and teaching of Turkology, language history and general linguistics. After the genius M. Kashghari and the great Mirza Kazim Bey, he is one of our most famous scholars in the field of Turkish language and literature. In this sense, it was B. Chobanzade who founded the first academic school of linguistics in Azerbaijan. B. Chobanzade, who was one of the main organizers of the 1st Turkological congress held in Baku in 1926, is the author of books such as: "Turk-tatar lisaniyyetine medkhel", "Turk-tatar dialektolojisi", "Turk grameri", "Krim-tatar elmi-serfi" as well as dozens of scientific articles. But, the author of the first work on general linguistics in Azerbaijan was Professor Bekir Chobanzade, whose "Turk-tatar lisaniyyetine medkhel" is an exception. So, considering that this work was written in 1924, we can say that the foundation of general linguistics in Azerbaijan was laid in the 20s of the 20th century. Considered an event for its time, this work is the first investigation on general (theoretical) linguistics in Turkology [3].

Without exaggeration, it can be said that it is no exaggeration to say that starting from the 1950s, B. Chobanzade was the master of thought of the linguists who wrote fundamental works on various directions of Azerbaijani linguistics. B. Chobanzade's investigations on the issues of Azerbaijani linguistics is the main source of modern linguistic research. A. Demirchizade, M. Huseynzade, M. Shiraliyev, A. Abdullayev, T. Hajiyev, Y. Seyidov and other prominent linguists' source

of ideas of the well-known research on various problems of the Azerbaijani literary language is B. Chobanzade's scientific creativity [1. P. 46].

Neriman Narimanov's dictionary plays a very important role in the development and formation of the science of linguistics. In this dictionary not only the correct use of linguistic terms, but also their equivalents are shown [7]. He was published three books in 1899, and one of those books is the textbook "Turk-Azerbaijan dilinin muxteser serf-nehvi". Here, the author's goal was to create a brief, clear idea of the Azerbaijani language in the readers and students. The textbook was in accordance with positive scientific-methodical requirements. In addition, he wrote works "Nadanlig" (1894), "Dilin belasi" yaxud "Shamdan bey" (1895), "Bahadir ve Sona" (1896–1908), "Nadir sah" (1899), "Ailemi-nisvan" (1910), "Pir" (1913), "Bir kendin serguzeshi" (1915) and others which brought him fame. Y.M. Seyidov wrote: *Nariman Narimanov's works are distinguished from other works in linguistics. Excellent works have been written about linguistic terminology since the past, and thanks to these written works, we can clearly see the development and formation of linguistic terminology today* [9, p.23].

Prominent Turkologist, Professor Farhad Zeynalov (1929-1984) is one of the first Azerbaijani linguists who devoted all his works, in general, his whole life to the study of Turkish languages and Turkology. He can be considered the founder of modern Azerbaijani Turkology after a prominent linguist Bekir Chobanzade. The main instigator for the rise of Turkology to the level of science doctor of philology, professor Farhad Ramazan oghlu Zeynalov's services are very great.

The establishment of the Turkological school in Azerbaijan is connected with his name. In 1962, this great scientist, who became an associate professor of the Department of General Linguistics of the Azerbaijan State University (now BSU), created the Department of Turkology in the same university in 1969. He solved many existing problems in the field of Turkology with his research on the classification of main and auxiliary parts of speech in the Turkish languages, comparative grammar of the Turkish languages, ancient Turkish written monuments. Professor F.R. Zeynalov paid special attention to teaching Turkish languages at a high level, including the Azerbaijani language, which belongs to the Oghuz language group. His investigations in the field of research of Turkish languages created conditions for researching and teaching our native language in a more perfect form. Professor F.R. Zeynalov gave a consistent and systematic classification of the main and auxiliary parts of speech for the first time. Although he died at an early age, the Turkologist scientist left behind a rich scientific legacy. The researcher, whose scientific activity is related to the historical fields of Turkish languages and the Azerbaijani language, is the author of 11 books and 70 scientific articles. Investigations conducted by the scientist during his scientific-pedagogical activities have found its reflection in his articles and theses as well as his monographs and textbooks such as: "Muasir turk dillərində baghləyijilər", "Turk dillerinin mugayiseli grammatikasi", "Turkologiyenin esaslari", "Muasir

turk dillerinde komekchi adlar", "Muasir turk dillerinde goshmalar", "Muasir turk dillerinde modal sozler", "Soz sonluglari leksikgrammatik kategoriya kimi", "Turk dillerinde sifetin kategoriyalari, ifade formalari" etc.. All his works were written in the direction of solving current problems in linguistics according to his time. The textbook "Turkologiyenin esaslari" published in 1981 is of special importance. This book aroused the interest of students as an excellent textbook not only in the universities of our country, but also in some universities of Turkey. In the textbook extensive information is provided about the origin and language characteristics of the Turkish languages, and the alphabet of the Turkish languages is grouped by periods. Farhad Zeynalov's services in the field of Turkology are priceless and undeniable.

Farhad Zeynalov also tried his hand in the field of textual studies, and together with Samat Alizade, he compiled the scientific-critical text of the epic "Kitabi Dede Gorgud" with an extensive introduction. "Kitabi-Dede Gorgud ve dunya shergshunasligi", "Dastani-Ahmadi Harami – Azerbaycanin en gedim edebi abidesi" etc. scientific works are valuable scientific sources in the study of our language history [1, p. 16]. One of the main points worth noting is that F. Zeynalov connected the subject of all his works dedicated to Turkology with the Azerbaijani language. He raised the research of the Azerbaijani language to the level of Turkology and thereby he laid the groundwork for other Turkologists to comment on existing problems to express their opinion.

A well-known scientist with a special place in the Azerbaijani linguistics, a phenomenon researcher of our language, an academician of national and international academies, an honored scientist of Azerbaijan, a laureate of the State award, the founder of the school of onomastics in Azerbaijan, a wonderful pedagogue, a real or honorary member of many scientific societies and organizations Afad Mahammad oglu Gurbanov has a special place in the history of the development of the Azerbaijan linguistic science. There is no field of linguistics that cannot be excluded from the research of a scientist.

Afad Gurbanov, who made great contributions to the development of the Azerbaijani linguistics, comprehensive research and teaching of the language, is the author of "Azerbayjan edebi ve danishig dili" (1965), "Muasir Azerbayjan edebi dili" (1967), "Umumi dilchilitch" (I, II cildler -1988,1993), "Poetik onomastika" (1988), "Azerbayjan dilinin onomalojiyasi" (1988), "Azerbayjan onomastika meseleleri" (1986), "Dunyanın dil aileleri" (1994), "Muasir Azerbayjan edebi dili" (2003), "Azerbayjan dilchiliyi problemleri" (Baki, 2004), "Azerbayjan onomalojiyasının esaslari", 2 cildde, (Baki-2004) and a number of monographs and textbooks, up to 500 scientific articles.

A. Gurbanov is a well-known scientist in the field of linguistics. He had great services in the field of general linguistics almost in the 20th century. In the history of world linguistics, he ranks with the scientists such as Panini, Xu Shen, Franz Bopp, Jacob Grimm, Wilhelm von Humboldt, Francois Champolin, Baudouin de

Courtenay, Carl Fossler, Ferdinand de Saussure, Franz Boas, Leonard Bloomfield.

A. Gurbanov's books are dedicated to the explanation and investigation of the theoretical and practical problems facing modern linguistics. While determining the state of development of Azerbaijani linguistics and its prospects, he clarified the science and its characteristics, issues of the creation of science, the formation of linguistics on two – linguistic and philosophical theoretical bases, the problem of classification of sciences, and the problems of defining the history of linguistics. The textbook "Muasir Azərbaycan edebi dili" which was published four times, has attracted attention not only in our country, but also abroad since its first publication. The well-known Turkologist A. Kononov wrote a review for this work and praised it highly. He wrote: *Afad Gurbanov's book "Muasir Azərbaycan edebi dili" reflects not only Azerbaijani literary language materials, but also topics related to the Turkish language materials* [1. p. 54]. In this book, the author has explained the Azerbaijani literary language materials in detail.

The book "Umumi dilchilich" is Afad Gurbanov's masterpiece. That book consists of 7 chapters: "Dilchilich elmi", "Dilchiliyin inkishafi", "Dilchiliyin sahələri", "Dilchiliyin shobeleri", "Dilin mahiyyəti", "Dilin mensheyi", "Dil və yazı". This textbook quickly became popular, attracted the attention of the scientific community, and was highly valued by many scientists. The book was also received positively in the former Soviet Union. Even V.I. Kodukhov, a professor of the University of Leningrad (now St. Petersburg) and a linguist, was interested in the same book. After getting acquainted with the book, he called the work *a product of original ideas*.

The book "Umumi dilchilich" that was published first was Afad Gurbanov's concept in the field of general linguistics. He confirmed this concept both after teaching this subject for a long time and after getting acquainted with the concepts of world scientists in this field. Afad Gurbanov reworked those works. As a result, he created the 2-volume work "Umumi dilchilich" which is the result of tireless work. The second edition of both volumes of the book was published in 2004, and the third edition was published in 2014 with a beautiful and elegant design. About the presentation of the 2004 edition of the work in the same year, Z. Guliyev's article entitled "Umumi dilchilich" kitabının təqdimatı" was published in "Azerbaijan" magazine (March 15, 2005). All fields of general linguistics are reflected in this two-volume fundamental work. Here, it can be said that the most pressing problems of world linguistics are covered in detail.

The terms expressing concepts related to the development of each science cause certain changes in terms of semantics and functionality over time. In such cases, the inability of the terms to accurately express the concept, the creation of synonymy, and the appearance of terminological defects made the author think as a specialist scientist. Because the lack of precision of the term creates confusion in the science itself. Taking this into account, the author uses the "vocabulary composition" of the language instead of the "vocabulary

fund", the "philosophical basis" instead of the methodology/methodological basis, the broad meaning of the term "dialect", as well as clarified and specified the meaning of a number of terms such as a series of onomastics – onomastics, onomalogy, ethnonymics, ethnonymy, toponymics, toponymy, anthroponymics, anthroponymy, hydronymics, hydronymy.

In terms of expanding the horizons of linguistics and defining its development areas, the role of onomastic research is great. In-depth research, analysis and scientific summarization of the onomastic lexicon, which has a special place in the vocabulary of the language, helps to solve the complex and necessary issues of our language and history. For the first time in Azerbaijani linguistics, the systematic solution and research of the issues of onomastics is related to the name by prof. Afad Gurbanov. Up to 100 of his articles on onomology have been published, including monographs such as "Azerbaijan onomasticasi", "Azerbaijan onomolojiya meseleleri", "Poetic onomastica", "Azerbaijan dilinin onomolojiyasi". Academician Mammadaga Shiraliyev writes in his article "Azerbajanda onomastika mektebi ve onun gelejeji". *"Azerbaijan dilinin onomolojiyasi" is very valuable not only for our linguistics, but also for world Turkological linguistics. I can say with full responsibility that Afad Gurbanov founded the School of Onomastics of Azerbaijan with this work* [4. p. 14].

The modern Azerbaijani literary language is one of the developed languages with a rich vocabulary. A large part of the vocabulary of this language is made up of the onomastic lexicon – a series of special names. The groups of words included in the onomastic lexicon are the product of certain social and historical development and are an invaluable wealth of words that reflect the life of the people to which they belong. A comprehensive research of the onomastic lexicon is very important for the study of fields of the modern language, dialectology, the language history, etc.

Afad Gurbanov's book "Azerbaijan onomalogiyasinin esaslari", which deals with the scientific-theoretical aspect of the problems of onomastics in Azerbaijani linguistics, was published in two volumes. The work was published both in Turkey and in Russia.

Since then, the author was interested in specific names (ethnonyms, hydronyms, zoonyms, cosmonyms and ktematonyms) systematically searched the formation and change of onomastic units, their stylistic features, orthographic and orthoepic problems in a theoretical way. In particular, a number of issues related to anthroponymics in onomastics – Azerbaijani personal names and their characteristics, the system of personal names, the structure of names, the composition of the origin of names, traditions of name selection and naming, rhyming of names, pronunciation of names – have been explained with specific facts. As we know, the history of human names is very ancient. Therefore, there are different divisions in world languages and Turkology regarding the formation of human names. Based on this, the author broadly explaining the unique sources and methods of formation of personal names used in the Azerbaijani language, divides them into two groups: a) pure Azerbaijani names; b) personal names of a foreign language origin.

Professor A. Gurbanov wrote: *“Each word should be thoroughly investigate. There is no meaningless word in the language and there cannot be, every word and phrase has a certain meaning. However, some words can have more than one meaning. Almost all personal names in our language are lexical units with appellative meaning. After the appellative word becomes an onomastic unit, it turns a proper name”* [4, p. 68]. In general, the research of anthroponymic units has taken an important place in the creativity of the scientist, the issues of anthroponymics have been investigated in the historical-linguistic direction, and he tried to eliminate the problems in this field.

Gurbanov is a scientist with scientific creativity covering almost all fields of linguistics. His research interests include the modern Azerbaijani literary language, Turkological linguistics, the language universals, general linguistics, onomology, lexicology, speech culture, translation studies, the language of literary works, stylistics, and higher education pedagogy and methodology.

Academician Aghamusa Akhundov is one of our scientists who created a school in the Azerbaijani linguistics. A. Akhundov is the author of such works *“Dil ve uslub meseleleri”*, *“Felin zamanlari”*, *“Dilchiliye girish”*, *“Umumi dilchilitch”*, *“Riyazi dilchilitch”*, *“Azerbaijan dilinin foneticasi”*, *“Dil ve edebiyat”* (in 2 volumes), *“Azerbaijan dilinin izahli lugheti*. These works are dedicated to the current problems of language history, the modern structure of the Azerbaijani language, the language theory, and general linguistics.

The world-wide Azerbaijani linguist – Aghamusa Akhundov said: *“The Azerbaijani language is my destiny. If you love it like your mother tongue, it is also my art. It's my sleepless nights, my searches”* [11].

In the creativity of A. Akhundov his monograph *“Azerbaijan dilinin fonemler sistemi”* can be especially noted. For the first time, the scientist summarized the phonetic system of the Azerbaijani language on the basis of experimental analysis and presented it at the theoretical level. In the creativity of A. Akhundov a language and society, a language and culture, social differentiation of the language, sociological aspects of the language evolution, language system, actual problems of the language system which attract worldwide attention related to general linguistics and language theory have been solved. For the first time in Azerbaijani linguistics, methods and methodology, sociological, logical, psychological, physiological, acoustic, distributive, mathematical, statistical research methods of learning the language have been defined. Aghamusa Akhundov was published the book *“Umumi dilchilich”*, the masterpiece of his scientific creativity. In the book, a brief history of the science of linguistics is given, the philosophical and social issues of the language are illuminated, the internal system and structure of the language, and the methods of linguistics are analyzed.

To study the actual problems of the Azerbaijani language, which has an ancient history, to reveal the social nature of the language, its specific mechanism objectively, to raise our language to a high level of development from Mirza Kazimbey and made prominent intellectuals and scientists of our nation think until today.

In the 20th century, with the academic researches of B. Chobanzadeh, Azerbaijani linguistics, in general, Turkology entered a new stage of development, and an army of highly respected linguists and Turkologists was created in Azerbaijan. In this sense, one of the founders of Azerbaijani Turkology is the outstanding linguist Alovzat Abdullayev. He had a unique creative concept. Scientific works of the scientist were published in Germany, France, Turkiye, Russia and Central Asian countries and caused great interest. A. Abdullayev, who has a wide range of creativity, is not only engaged in one field of linguistics, but also phonetics, orthography, etymology, historical grammar, morphology, syntax, speech culture, etc., and created significant works dedicated to the most current problems of Turkology as a whole. Specialization and additional categories, adverbs, predicates, complex sentences of mixed type, transformation of constituent parts of subordinate complex sentences and other issues were compiled by him for the first time and included in the higher school program. A. Abdullayev, a state prize winner, a full member of the Turkish Language Institute, a member of the International Congress of Altai Scholars, rendered invaluable services in the training of many Turkologist scholars in Azerbaijan and outside the borders of our country. Prof. Mehman Musaoğlu writes: *“Azerbaijani Linguistics in the Context of Turkish Linguistics and Prof. Dr. Elövset Abdullayev's article titled “The School of Vocabulary”...12 years...during the period of the Soviet Union, and after that, during the time I worked in Turkiye, I always identified myself as the famous linguist Türkologist Prof. Dr. As a representative and student of Elovset Abdullayev's school, I always tried to continue where my teacher left off... Turkishness= Turkish knowledge= Turkish language knowledge= Turkish grammar and linguistic knowledge... [1, p25].*

One of our prominent scientists is Honored Scientist, State Prize Laureate, Corresponding Member of ANAS, Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor Abdulazal Demirchizade. Demirchizade who was a student of the great Turkologist, professor Bekir Chobanzade school, gave valuable information about the rules of orthography in the book *“Azerbaijan dili orfoepiyasinin esaslari”* published in 1969. The scientist, throughout his creativity, expressed his objection to inappropriate foreign words in the language and convey his attitude to this problem in his works. The author dedicated the books *“Dilin lughet terkibi hagginda”* (1952), *“50 soz”* (1962), *“Muasir Azerbaijan dilinin esas lughet terkibi və grammatic gurulushu”* (1965), *“Azerbaijan dilinin uslubiyati”* (1962) to the investigation of the vocabulary of the Azerbaijani language. In these works, he tried to carefully summarize his ideas about words and meaning, the lexical and grammatical meaning of the words, vocabulary, the main and additional parts of the vocabulary, general, necessary and special characteristics each of them. It is possible to get enough information from these works to learn the rules of development and enrichment of the vocabulary. He did his best in the field of initial research of problems related to the grammatical structure of the language, morphology and especially syntax.

These works of A. Demirchizade are important sources in the study of lexicology.

A. Demirchizade is the author of the textbook "Muasir Azerbaijan dili" (phonetics), which is included in the gold fund of our linguistics. More than twenty his books and more than two hundred his scientific articles have been published. In these writings, the scientist expressed his opinion on linguistic issues such as phonetics, etymology, stylistics, etc. The author's "Azerbaijan dili tarixi xulaseleri" (1938), "M.F.Akhundov dil hagginda ve Akhundovun dili" (1941), "Azerbaijan dilinin tarixi" (1948), "Azerbaijan edebi dilinin inkishaf yollari" (1959) etc. books are valuable scientific sources for studying the history of our language.

Prominent linguist of Azerbaijan, the creativity of academician Tofiq Hajiyev, who became a full member of ANAS, is wide and multifaceted. Academician Tofiq Hajiyev's services in the development of the Azerbaijani education, enlightenment, Turkology are unexamined. The textbook "Azerbaijan edebi dilinin tarixi" by the eminent scientist was published in 1976. In 2012, the author reprinted the mentioned work. Using the works of our valuable classics and ancient manuscripts, he studied the creation, formation of the Azerbaijani literary language, its norms and styles at a high level.

The textbook "History of Azerbaijani Literary Language" by the eminent scientist was published in 1976. In 2012, the author reprinted the mentioned work. Using the works of our valuable classics and ancient manuscripts, he studied the creation and formation of the Azerbaijani literary language, its norms and styles at a high level. It is possible to say that the history of the literary language in Azerbaijan improved and became more widespread starting from the 19th century. The 19th century is a turning point in the history of socio-economic and cultural development of the Azerbaijani people. Tofiq Hajiyev writes: *"One of the cultural achievements of the era is the development of the press, which is a strong impetus to the popularization of the national literary language"* [1. p.40]. The eminent scientist emphasizes that the press polished the literary language and created a perfect norm, applied and stabilized this norm, preaches to the readership and promotes it. The norms of the literary language are a historical event and it is formed in connection with the process of formation of the nation, the national language. Enrichment of the vocabulary of the literary language, introduction of borrowed words into the language is realized through journalistic style. Therefore, journalistic style is considered the most popular style of literary language. If earlier the artistic style was the leading style, after the journalistic style emerged, it became the leading style of the Azerbaijani literary language. So, at the same time the journalistic style brings the literary language closer to the colloquial language and acts as an active tribune of the struggle for the national language. But all these directs to a new direction of the future development of publicist style, which occupies an important place in the system of styles. Academician T. Hajiyev's textbook "Azerbaijan edebi dilinin tarixi" is priceless for studying the historical landscape of journalistic style.

Professor Yusif Mirahmed oglu Seyidov, who gave a new direction to Azerbaijani linguistics and had a great role in the teaching and development of morphology and syntax, systematically dealt with grammar. The honored scientist was one of the great scientists who always took care of the purity of our language and carried out serious propaganda in this field. Among the main services of the linguist, due to his scientific content and methodological excellence, more than two hundred scientific works, more than thirty books dedicated to the theoretical and applied issues of linguistics, including that prepared and were published for the students of the Faculty of Philology such as "Muasir Azerbaijan dili" IV parts, "Sintaxis", "Azerbaijan dilinin grammatikasi", "Morfolojiya" and etc. takes the main place as the author of high school textbooks. Professor Yusif Seyidov, who played an exceptional role in the development of Azerbaijani linguistics, was one of the scientists distinguished by the breadth of his research in the field of literary studies, as well as linguistics. He created a concise chronicle of the linguistic and literary studies of the Azerbaijani people in his works "Yazichi ve dil", "Sozun shohreti", "Sozun gudreti", "Sozun hikmeti" etc. collected and systematized the opinions of Azerbaijani writers who lived in the XI-XX centuries about words and language [1, 42].

One of our scientists who has conducted serious research in the field of general linguistics in Azerbaijan is Abulfaz Rajabli, professor of the Department of General Linguistics of Baku State University. A. Rajabli's first research on general linguistics was the book "Dilchiliye girishden tapshiriglar", which he was published in 1979. Although the book is small in volume, it is valuable in terms of being the first work of a young researcher. After that, he consistently dealt with general linguistic issues and published a large-volume book called "Dilchilich tarixi". This book has attracted the attention of experts due to a number of parameters and has been highly appreciated. It should also be noted that the author continued his research on this work and was published it in two volumes. In a comparison of both publications, the integral elements exceed the differential elements. The differential elements show themselves in the fact that in the final version of the work, the discussions about

V. von Humboldt and F. dö Sössür were completely rewritten.

Rajabli can be compared with any classical linguist in the world in terms of the number of books which he wrote in the field of general linguistics. Scientist's Books such as: "Nezeri dilchilich", "Dilchilich metodlari", "Struktur dilchilich", "Sosiolingvistica", "Tipoloji dilchilich", "Universaliler dilchiliyi", "V.fon Humboldt – umumi dilchiliyin banisi kimi", "U.D.Uitni-linqvist kimi", "F.dö Sossurun dilchilich gorushleri" have become table books for scientists, teachers, and students in terms of studying general linguistic issues in Azerbaijan. A. Rajabli is considered an innovative scientist mostly due to his Turkological research.

Azerbaijani linguistics, which does not lag behind world linguistics and Turkology is developing on a rising line. Azerbaijani linguistics, which was laid the

foundation in the Middle Ages, developing very rapidly increased its reputation. In the following periods, our scientific grammar was formed, linguists with strong potential were trained, new areas of our linguistics appeared, the theoretical level of our linguistics increased, and its application expanded.

As a result, it was analyzed that the onomastic lexicon makes up a large part of the vocabulary of the modern Azerbaijani literary language, and that the vocabulary reflecting the life of the people it belongs to and included in the onomastic lexicon being an invaluable wealth of words. It was understood that it is necessary to conduct new research in order to succeed in solving the ontological and methodological problems of linguistics, to conquer new horizons in the philosophy of the language and the philosophy of linguistics, to reveal and show the connection of linguistics with society, literature, culture, informatics and other fields.

It was clarified that it is necessary to bring the world heritage of linguistics to our country along with the creation of a strong material base that ensures the future development of our linguistics. Regarding the position of our independent state in the world civilization in modern times, it was analyzed that it is necessary to study and teach our language both inside the country and abroad, as well as the integration of Azerbaijani linguistics into the world linguistics.

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